
Open Design Methodology in Mass Housing through Investigation of End-Users' Housing Physical Cues Preferences

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Abstract

Open Design Methodology is defined as a way of preserving the strength and integrity of the design concept while keeping it open for emerging and evolving expectations; hence, is capable of enhancing homemaking in mass housing, especially in developing countries, e.g. Iran and Malaysia whereby end-users are absent during the housing delivery process. This study aims at explaining the implication of Open Design Methodology in enhancing sense of home in mass housing through studying end-users' perceptions of housing physical cues. Accordingly, the collected data through a survey of housing physical cues preferences conducted on 116 Iranian students of Universiti Teknologi Malaysia living at least one year in mass housing apartments was analyzed, using Exploratory Factor Analysis and One Sample t-test. The seven extracted factors from Exploratory Factor Analysis were hierarchically classified into three levels using One Sample t-test. In addressing the aim of the study, the results of One Sample t-test shed light on end-users' perceptions, making it possible to address two different areas of decision-making in mass housing namely professional and ordinary. Dealing with abstract, subjective, complicated, and multidimensional physical cues, the first area is far beyond ordinary end-users' knowledge, profession, and skill; hence the supervisory role of professionals is highly recommended. The second area deals with concrete and tangible physical features, which has the potential to be left open for end-users' gradually progressive decision making, and according to their evolving and emerging needs.

Keywords: Mass Housing, Open Design Methodology, Housing Components Physical Cues, End-users' Perception, Sense of Home

1. Introduction

A home is a place for responding to residents' emotional and spiritual demands, prior to their physiological needs. Homemaking, in this sense, means to improve sense of home in living environments. This study aims at explaining the capability of Open Design Methodology (ODM) in enhancing "sense of home" in mass housing by providing motivationally congruent physical settings in the mass housing environment. Improving the congruity of the physical settings with residents' motivations is also capable of enhancing housing efficiency by improving end-users' environmental choice behaviours and the related environmental impacts, along with reducing the costs of post-occupancy interventions (Jusan, 2007, 2010).

In the context of developing countries like Iran and Malaysia, although mass housing is the major solution to the problem of housing shortage, and this dwelling type is highly popular among people from various socio-economic groups, homemaking in mass housing is a problematic challenge because of absence and inaccessibility of end-users during the housing decision making, especially in the early stages of feasibility assessment and design process. In this situation, ODM is a suitable methodology for solving the problem by its conceptual capacity in providing a flexible design paradigm and gradually progressive methodology.

In responding to the aim of the study, it is necessary to explain to what extents ODM is beneficial in homemaking in mass housing. Indeed, the main assumption in explaining the implication of ODM in homemaking in mass housing is the degree of complexity and readability of human perceptions, which would be achieved by studying end-users' housing components physical cues (HCPC) preferences.

For this purpose, the study conducted based on a survey of the end-users' preferences of housing components physical cues. Physical cues of housing components are the most visible aspects of built environments, which contain a broad range of information about the meaning and function of the components; hence, have essential roles in creating particular characteristics for the different places, and have the potential to reflect the occupants' perceptions (Schulz, 1985; Reis & Lay, 2009; Asad Poor, 2014). Therefore, the investigation of the physical cues preferences has the potential in explaining the implication of ODM in enhancing homemaking in mass housing.

This paper initially represents a brief discussion on human perceptual organisms in conjunction with the physical cues, then provides an overview of the concept of ODM as the conceptual platform for the study. Eventually, conducting Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) and One-Sample t-test over the collected data from the survey, the paper explains the role of the cues in reflecting end-users' perceptions. The discussion

of the analyses sheds light on the implication of ODM in responding to the demands for homemaking in mass housing.

2. Literature Review

There is a long line of tradition on the association between housing components physical cues and end-users' motivations (Beckham, 2007; Loeb, 2007; Norberg-Schulz, 1985). Schulz (1985) stressed the role played by the physical features of housing components, e.g. window and wall in a dwelling unit in creating a unique spatial characteristic, affecting the overt and latent functions of the components, and enhancing the meaning and use of the dwelling places. Beckham (2007) also stressed the effect of location, orientation, position, and form as different physical features of an architectural element, e.g. porch in the creation of the different personal, communal, and memorial functions and meaning for the place. Loeb (2007) explained the role of window, not only as a source of light, but also as an appropriate element, with various personal, social, and domestic functions, e.g. interaction with outside, a frame for entertainment and imagination, a location for visual interactions, and a place for performing a wide range of household activities. The common ground provided by the conducted studies over and above their different theoretical assumptions and methodological praxis is the role of the physical cues of the components in representing various human motivations.

Appearance, visual composition, and symbolic features are the three major sources in addressing the housing components physical cues (Reis & Lay, 2009). These three categories represent the three main levels of individuals' perceptions and judgments in evaluating their surrounding environments (Lang, 1987; Nasar, 1994). Among them, visual composition and appearance are extracted directly from formal and sensory features respectively. The third level that is also defined as the image of building deals with associational values is extracted indirectly from formal and sensory cues (Allen & Ng, 1999).

Visual composition of building points to the demand for order in the visual organization (Prak, 1977; Lang, 1987); hence, deals with the structure of form and its geometric qualities (Lang, 1987), or presentational properties of an object through perceptual processes (Reis & Lay, 2009). The visual composition includes variables such as form, shape, size, proportion, depth, location, rhythm, complexity, and flexibility. Perception of order implies a perception of unity and structure in the organization of the elements or spatial adequacy; hence, results in similar perceptual reactions in different individuals independent of their cultural backgrounds (Reis & Lay, 2009).

The appearance of building deals with the sensory aesthetics, which is related to the pleasurable sensations received from the surface properties of the environment, and depends on the arousal of individual's perceptual systems arising from the effect of variables like colour, odour, sound, material, transparency, and texture (Lang, 1988). At this level, the process of perception relates sensory experiences with the environment. The sensory level deals with the pleasurable sensation rooted in the collection of built and natural morphological elements in a certain place, alongside the aspects related to maintenance and cleanliness (Reis & Lay, 2009).

However, the image of a place is defined as the spiritual picture of the place created by symbolic contents rooted in individual's cognitive process (Lynch, 1960). Concerning symbolic meanings, a person is able to experience buildings through a variety of content variables reflecting his/her internal representations of the building, and meaning of these representations with regard to his/her memories, beliefs, ideals, dreams, and values (Rapoport, 2000). Accordingly, symbolic meanings encompass two interrelated levels, including denotative and connotative values (Reis & Lay, 2009; Nasar, 1994). An individual first recognizes the denotative meaning, i.e. type or style, then infers the connotative meaning, i.e. like or dislike (Reis & Lay, 2009). Symbolic meanings are deeply originated from individuals' past experiences and cognitive judgments; hence, result in a variety of expressions among different people with different socio-cultural backgrounds (Table 1).

Table 1: Categorization of Housing Component Physical Cues

Features	Samples	Concept	Characteristics
Visual Composition	Formal Features, i.e. Form, Shape, Size, Proportion, Location, Rhythm, Complexity, Flexibility	The need for order, structure and unity in visual perception	Perceptual Does not imply endless repetition, but implies the existence of well-coordinated variety, or unity and variety. Almost same for different person
Appearance	Sensory Features, i.e. Colour, Odour, Sound, Material, Transparency, Brightness, Textures	Collection of built and natural morphological elements in certain place, and aspects related to maintenance and cleanliness	Perceptual Perceived by 5 sensorial channels of individual, i.e. smell, touché, hear, etc. The process of perception relates to sensory experience with the environment Almost same for different person

Image	Denotative	Symbolic Values	Content variables that reflect individual's internal representations of the building, and meaning of these representations	Cognitive
	Type, Style	The both sensory and visual feature, with association of particular judgments about their cognitive meaning		
	Connotative			
	Like, Dislike			vary among different individuals

In sum, the first two levels deal with utilitarian meanings, while the third level deals with symbolic content. The formal and sensory features are perceptual; hence, they are functionally autonomous from the cognitive process, are relatively concrete, tangible, and objective, and result in almost similar reactions in different people (Lang1987; Nasar, 1994; Allen and Ng, 1999). The symbolic features are cognitive to the extent that they depend strongly on person's denotative inferences and connotative judgments. Thus, in comparison with the first two levels, the symbolic features are quite subjective and abstract, exerting higher levels of complexity (Reis & Lay, 2009; Allen and Ng, 1999). Indeed, sensory and formal features are the main sources in explaining utilitarian and symbolic contents.

Between the first two levels, the formal features address the adequacy of the spatial structure and organization, while the sensory cues highlight the pleasurable of the space in relation to its compatibility with the surrounding environment and sense of maintenance and cleanness (Reis & Lay, 2009). Therefore, the complexity and multidimensionality of the features related to the visual composition seem to be relatively higher than the appearance, as the motivations related to the spatial adequacy are more complicated than those related to the visual pleasurable. Consequently, the readability of the perceptual aspects related to the sensory features would be higher than the aspects related to the formal features.

In this study, a number of formal and sensory features were employed to the extent that they are the main sources in representing human perceptions, i.e. their perceptual inferences and cognitive judgments. In conducting the research, among the different physical features, shape/form, proportion, size, location, complexity, and flexibility were considered as the selected formal cues, while material, colour, texture, transparency were considered as the selected sensory cues.

3. Open Design Methodology

ODM conceptually is a gradually progressive design paradigm, which works based on the premise of preserving the strength and conceptual integrity of the core design concept while keeping it open for demanding, evolving, and changing requirements,

and handling the emerging constraints in innovative ways (Tellioglu, et al., 1998). In this regard, ODM makes designers able to work within an open space of possibility scenarios, rather than absolutely fixed solutions. The centrality of the concept is to consider the dynamic interplay between various design actions, e.g. opening, expanding, fixing, constraining, re-opening, and monitoring. Openness provides the possibility of a gradually progressive development, enhancing the congruity of the environmental characteristics with end-users' emerging and fluctuating requirements (Tellioglu, et al., 1998).

The focal point of this paper is to explain the implication of ODM in improving homemaking in mass housing by explaining the end-users' perception, which is a highly critical subject in differentiating the area of professionals and ordinary end-users in mass-housing decision making (Asad Poor, 2015). The centrality of the end-users' perception makes the study able to explain the implication of the openness in the representation of the different motivations of the end-users in the different stages of mass housing decision making.

4. Sampling Design

The sampling population of the study was Iranian students of Universiti Teknologi Malaysia (UTM). In selecting this social unit, a number of parameters (de Vaus, 2002), i.e. their future life aspirations, housing expectations, knowledge, and perceptual ability were also taken into account for the sampling design (Kenyon, 2002; Sixsmith, 1986).

According to Kenyon (2002), a homogeneous group of younger people in their transitional age toward adulthood and maturity were suitable sampling population to the extent that compared with other age groups, they are more likely to consider their intrinsic motivations regardless of socio-economic constraints, e.g. economic and financial sources, availability of physical infrastructure and amenities, or their dependence on a social group, relatives, and family members. However, in investigating the psychological aspects of the built environment, although home ownership is an interesting parameter in generating more reliable outcomes, the economic performance of the housing market does not allow the selected age category to live in such housing tenure conditions (Sepehrdoust & Berjisian, 2011). Moreover, the socio-cultural constraints imposed by the society of mass housing residents detract from the attention of mass-housing residents to their intrinsic motivations, though they might be homeowners. The owners' housing experiences and preferences are mostly affected by the rules and regulations imposed by the various external agents and authorities, e.g. government, management system, and other stakeholders and organizations related to the mass housing community (Stanley, 2009).

The study selected Iranian students who study abroad, far from their family, because they lived independently, and enjoyed from autonomy, freedom, and a new level of intimacy, and their expected job, economic and financial status, along with their future life aspirations allowed them in having realistic images about their future home based on their intrinsic motivations and regardless of the impacts of external agents, though they were living in transitional, non-conducive, unfamiliar, and unstable environments, (Kenyon, 2002; Yusuff, 2011). Their age and education level, current living conditions, and future life aspirations were the different parameters in selecting this population group as an interesting social unit for the purpose of this study. Finally, Iranian students of UTM who lived in mass housing apartments outside the university campus in Skudai, Malaysia for the period of at least one year were selected as the sampling population.

5. Research Methodology

Addressing the end-users' preferences is a suitable analytical model for studying their perceptions to the extent that regardless of its hypothetical nature, the model is applicable in the absence of actual, adequate, and sufficient data (Opoku & Abdul-Muhmin, 2010). According to the analytical model, the respondents were supposed to express their preferences about the role of the housing component physical cues in their housing selection through 6-Points Likert's scaling technique (Chomeya, 2010).

Collecting the respondents' HCPCs preferences, the latent structure among the physical cues was initially identified by categorizing the variables into fewer factors through Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA). The extracted factors were then labelled based on the characteristics of the physical cues (Field, 2009).

The composite scores of the factors were also computed and used as input data in subsequent analyses. The means of the composite scores highlighted the relative importance of the factors. Then, one-sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov test was then conducted on the extracted factors to test the normality of the collected data to make sure the randomization of data gathering (Field, 2009; Steyn, 2015). One-Sample t-test was also employed to examine if the hierarchically arranged means are significantly important for the respondents' preferences (Opoku & Abdul-Muhmin, 2010). The analytical model of the study assists in explaining the respondents' perceptions by explaining the characteristics of the respondents' preferences, i.e. possibility of hierarchical arrangements, increasing multidimensionality and complexity of the factors, alongside multi-functionality of HCPCs.

6. Data Collection

The ten selected physical cues of five architectural elements, i.e. door, wall, window, floor, and ceiling are the main sources in developing 50 independent variables of a

self-administered questionnaire. The study employed probability random sampling to make sure that the samples are representative of the whole population (Kothari, 2009, De Vaus, 2002). The respondents were supposed to evaluate the level of importance of the variables in their housing selection preferences based on their intrinsic motivations regardless of the effect of external agents, e.g. economic and financial matters, and socio-cultural limitations.

116 out of the total 130 filled questionnaires were considered as the properly answered questionnaires and were employed in the subsequent analyses. The sampling population included 68 men (58.6%) and 48 women (41.4%), 51 of them were single (44%), and 65 people were married (56%). The three age categories of the respondents included 26-35 years old that was the largest group, with 81 people (69.8%), older than 36 years old, with 20 people (17.3%), and finally 18-25 years old, with 15 people (12.9%) (Table 2). The majority of the respondents (88%) were from the postgraduate level, including PhD and master students, with respectively 48.3% and 39.7% of the entire population. The other educational status included the participants who had graduated at the period of the survey. Moreover, 78.9% of the participants' experienced unstable financial situations (62.3% had no income and 16.6% received an income of less than \$500), and only 21.1% of them experienced a relatively stable economic status by receiving more than \$500 (Table 2).

Table 2: Respondents' demographic characteristics

Demographic Characteristics		Frequency	Percent (%)
Gender	Male	68	58.6
	Female	48	41.4
Marital Status	Single	51	44
	Married	65	56
Age Group	18-25	15	12.9
	26-35	81	69.8
	>36	20	17.3
Education level	PhD student	56	48.3
	Master student	46	39.7
	Bachelor student	4	3.4
	Others	10	8.6

Income per Month	<\$ 500	19	16.6
	\$ 500-1500	20	17.5
	>\$1500	4	3.6
	Without any income	72	62.3

7. Results and Discussion

Before running EFA, One Sample t-test was conducted on all 50 variables to determine if HCPCs were significantly important for the respondents' preferences (Field, 2009). In conducting One Sample t-test the scale mid-point of 3.5 was considered as the transition point between not important and important as shown in (Opoku and Abdul-Muhmin, 2010). In total, all the variables were identified as significantly important ($p < 0.001$) except, i.e. floor transparency, complexity, and location, alongside ceiling location and flexibility ($p > 0.05$), which were removed from the list for the subsequent analysis.

Factor analysis of the remaining 45 HCPCs was then conducted to reduce the number of variables, and to detect the latent structure among the variables. For this purpose, EFA was conducted by using principle components (PC) extraction method with varimax rotation. Factors with eigenvalues greater than one were retained if in the rotated component matrix their factor loadings were greater than 0.45. Since the sample size was 116 people, the factor loading score of 0.45 was selected to make sure the validity of the outcome of the EFA (Field, 2009).

Initially, the factorability of the 45 variables was tested by using a number of well-recognized criteria. Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin measure of sampling adequacy was 0.686, which highlighted a proper level of factorability to the extent that it was greater than 0.6 (the recommended value of factorability). Bartlett's test of sphericity was also significant (2636.526, $p < 0.001$), and communalities of the variables were above 0.5, which confirms there are some common variances among the items. Regarding these overall indicators of factorability, EFA was conducted with all 45 variables (Field, 2009). Initially, 14 factors were retained from the 45 variables, explaining 74.1% of the variance in the variables.

The number of the extracted factors was quite high, some of which consisted of only one variable, and the outputs were not interpretable. Therefore, the analysis was continuously repeated so that a reasonable number of factors with at least three variables for each of them, and a proper level of interpretability were obtained (Field, 2009; Larry Hatcher, 2005). Seven factors were eventually extracted, which explained 54.08% of the variance in the variables.

The categorization of the variables highlighted the presence of the different sensory (appearance) and formal cues (visual composition) in separate groups. Therefore, the factors were labelled Formal Cues 1 to 3 and Sensory Cues A to D (Table 3). The next highlighted characteristic of the extracted factors was the similarity in the function and the level of complexity of the features presented in each factor. These outputs are somehow highly fruitful in addressing the readability of the respondents' perceptions based on their HCPCs preferences; hence, have the potential of explaining ODM in enhancing homemaking in mass housing.

Table 3: Factors Extracted from housing physical cues

No	Variables (Physical Cues)	Factor Loading
Formal Cues 1	Floor Proportion	0.835
	Ceiling Proportion	0.799
	Floor Size	0.759
	Floor Form	0.720
	Wall Proportion	0.714
	Ceiling size	0.773
	Wall Size	0.588
	Ceiling Complexity	0.561
	Ceiling Form	0.521
	Wall Complexity	0.484
	Floor Flexibility	0.476
	Door Transparency	0.433
	Wall location	0.361
	Wall Form	0.360
Formal Cues 2	Window Location	0.834
	Window Proportion	0.739
	Window form	0.739
	Window Size	0.700
	Door Form	0.639
	Door Size	0.561
	Door Proportion	0.550
	Door Location	0.420

Formal Cues 3	Door Flexibility	0.822
	Window Flexibility	0.740
	Window Complexity	0.688
	Door Complexity	0.579
	Wall Flexibility	0.499
Sensory Cues A	Ceiling Colour	0.656
	Door Material	0.581
	Ceiling Material	0.576
	Wall Colour	0.533
	Floor Colour	0.512
	Floor Material	0.422
	Window Transparency	0.344
Sensory Cues B	Door Texture	0.588
	Window Texture	0.572
	Door Colour	0.540
	Window Colour	0.525
Sensory Cues C	Ceiling Transparency	0.681
	Wall Texture	0.593
	Wall Transparency	0.517
	Ceiling Texture	0.501
Sensory Cues D	Floor Texture	0.759
	Wall Material	0.599
	The Recoded Variable (Window Material)	0.478

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis

Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization

a. Rotation converged in 11 iteration

Extracting the factors through EFA, for a better explanation of the respondents' perceptions, it was also necessary to examine the hierarchical tendencies among the factors, and then to look at the characteristics of the classified factors in association with the overall characteristics of the physical features loaded in each category. To identify the relative importance of the factors, initially, the factors composite scores were computed to be used as input data for the subsequent analyses. The means of the composite factors highlighted the relative importance of the factors.

Before conducting one-sample t-test, a one sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov test was conducted to test the normality of the data distribution on the extracted factors. The results of the analysis showed that PHF1, $D(116) = 0.122$, $p > 0.05$, PHF2, $D(116) = 0.152$, $p > 0.001$ PHF3, $D(116) = 0.124$, $p > 0.05$, PHF4, $D(116) = 0.144$, $p > 0.05$, PHF5, $D(116) = 0.104$, $p > 0.05$, PHF6, $D(116) = 0.104$, $p > 0.05$, and PHF7, $D(116) = 0.159$, $p > 0.001$ were all significantly normal, confirming the randomization of the data gathering (Table4) (Field, 2009). The Kolmogorov-Smirnov test is suitable for samples less than 100, and for the bigger sample size, the test is significant even if the scores would be slightly different from the normal distribution (Field, 2009; Steyn, 2015).

Table 4. one-sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

		Formal Cues 1	Formal Cues 2	Formal Cues 3	Sensory Cues A	Sensory Cues b	Sensory Cues c	Sensory Cues d
N		116	116	116	116	116	116	116
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	0.122	0.152	0.124	0.144	0.104.	0.104	0.159
	Positive	0.079	0.100	0.062	0.065	0.079	0.063	0.089
	Negative	-0.122	-0.152	-0.124	-0.144	-0.104	-0.104	-0.159
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		1.319	1.634	1.315	1.552	1.121	1.123	1.712
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		0.062	0.01	0.063	0.016	0.162	0.160	0.006

Test distribution is Normal.

Then, One Sample t-tests were conducted to identify if the factors are significantly important from the scale mid-point of 3.5, which has a significant role in determining the level of importance of the different factors from the participants' perceptions point of view. The scale mid-point of 3.5 was the transition point between unimportant and important (Opoku and Abdul-Muhmin, 2010).

Table 5 shows the classification of the factors based on their means in descending order. Considering t-values of the factors and the significant level of the first four factors ($p < 0.001$), the means of these factors were significantly different from the scale point of 3.5; hence, they were considered as relatively important HCPCs factors. However, regarding the significant level of the last three factors ($p > 0.05$), they were considered as unimportant factors for the respondents' HCPCs preferences.

Table 5: Relative importance of factors

	Physical Cues	Factors	Mean	Std.D	t
1	Most important	Sensory Cues A	4.91	0.61	24.86
2		Formal Cues 2	4.91	0.82	18.57
3		Sensory Cues D	4.77	0.67	20.54
4	Important	Sensory Cues B	4.16	1.03	6.92
5	Unimportant	Sensory Cues C	3.52	0.99	0.233**
6		Formal Cues 1	3.44	1.8	-0.555**
7		Formal Cues 3	3.44	1.14	-0.596**

** $p > 0.05$, for all other factors t-value, $p < 0.001$

The extracted gaps between the calculated t-values made it also possible to classify the factors into three different levels, from very important to unimportant (Figure 1). The most important level includes Sensory Cues A, Formal Cues 2, and Sensory Cues D with t-values, respectively 24.86, 20.54, and 18.57. As the t-values dropped significantly, the second level with t-value 6.92 encompassed Sensory Cues B, which was highlighted as important level. The third level with the lowest t-values and the significance level higher than 0.05 included Sensory Cues C, Formal Cues 1, and Formal Cues 3 with t-values, respectively 0.233, -0.555, and -0.596, which were considered as unimportant factors. The first level included the most emphasized features, while the second level highlighted the moderately demanded, and the third level encompassed the aspects located out of concern of the respondents.

Figure 1. Relative importance of motivational factors extracted from HCPCs preferences, (Asad Poor, 2014).

The conducted analyses represent the potentials of the extracted factors in explaining ODM in association with end-users' motivations and homemaking in mass housing. For this purpose, the priority is to explain the hierarchical classification of the factors based on the characteristics of the variables loaded on each factor, e.g. the degree of complexity and multidimensionality of the different factors, multi-functionality of the variables, and the readability of the respondents' perceptions.

Moving down through the hierarchical arrangement, the pattern of HCPCs is switched from sensory cues into formal cues. Sensory cues are signs of pleasurable sensation from the compatibility of the built and natural elements, alongside maintenance and cleanliness of the environment, while formal cues are signs of order, geometrical quality, and spatial adequacy. Sensory features are relatively objective and concrete as they are perceived by the people's five senses, but the formal features are more likely to be abstract, subjective and complicated as they emphasize spatial structure and organization. Therefore, formal features require a higher level of expertise and profession compared with sensory features.

The only exception in the arrangement of the physical cues was happened on the most important level by the presence of Formal Cues 2 in this category. To explain the reason, it is beneficial to have a look at the characteristics of the variables loaded on this factor, which include location, size, and proportion of the door and window rather than the other elements like wall, floor, and ceiling, or the features like complexity and flexibility. The explanation is the priority, direct, and overt function of size, proportion, and location of the door and window in the respondents' dwelling requirements, e.g. visual, audial, and physical connection, communication, and relationships with the outside environments. That is why they have a proper level of experiences, and skills, as well as clear perceptions over the functions of these features. The formal features that are related to wall, floor, and ceiling or the concepts like complexity and flexibility that have a variety of complicated and latent functions are located out of concern of the respondents' housing preferences. From this viewpoint, the end-users are more interested in dealing with the pleasurable sensation rooted in the collection of built and natural morphological elements in their housing environment, the aspects related to maintenance and cleanliness, alongside the aspects that assist them in controlling the communication with the outside environments. Accordingly, the aspects related to the spatial order, organization, and structure are not in the area of the respondents' profession and expertise.

Consequently, the results highlight significant changes in the respondents' preference, from relatively ordinary levels toward quite more complicated and professional levels. In other words, the pattern of the respondents' perceptions is changed from relatively concrete and tangible features with high levels of readability and overt functions, e.g.

colour, texture, transparency, and brightness toward subjective, abstract, complicated, and multidimensional features with low level of readability and latent functions, e.g. form, shape, size, complexity, and flexibility. The findings highlight two different areas in the housing decision making, which have critical roles in explaining the implication of ODM in homemaking in the mass housing environments.

8. Conclusion

The results, in general, highlight the end-users' perceptions of HCPCs, which have the potential in explaining to what extents ODM would be more practically fruitful in enhancing homemaking in the mass housing environment. Regarding the end-users' perceptions, the hierarchical arrangement of HCPCs is changed from very important to unimportant through a specific pattern, from the cues with prior, direct and overt functional applications, less complexity and multidimensionality, alongside relatively ordinary levels to abstract, multidimensional, latent functional implications, high complexity and multidimensionality, as well as professional levels. In other words, moving down through the hierarchical levels leads to the increase in the level of complexity and multidimensionality of the factors, as well as multi-functionality of HCPCs. Eventually, the formal features are somehow out of concern of the ordinary respondents because of their higher complexity and different application areas, which necessitate a higher level of expertise and profession.

Accordingly, it is possible to differentiate the housing decision-making process into two different areas in the context of developing countries, e.g. Iran and Malaysia, whereby the end-users are mostly absent during the delivery process of mass housing. The first area is far beyond the knowledge, expertise, skill, and profession of ordinary people; hence, the professionals' assistantships and supervisions are essential. This level is capable of generating the stable core centre of the housing design. The second area includes relatively concrete and content-specific concepts, and is within the skills and knowledge of ordinary end-users; hence, should be left open for their future decision-making. While the first area is the professional level of decision making in mass housing, the second area is the ordinary level. The intervention of the physical cues at the ordinary level is reasonably and simply accessible for the end-users at any stages of the housing delivery (Asad Poor, 2014 & 2015, Jusan, 2010), and unlike the simplicity of the intervention, it is capable of improving the congruity of the spatial characteristics of the dwelling environments with the end-users' motivational tendencies, enhancing their sense of home as well (Stanley, 2009). In sum, it can be concluded that in the context of developing countries, the application of ODM would be more practically fruitful in improving sense of home in mass housing if the concept of openness assists in employing the ordinary end-users'

knowledge, skill and profession in responding to their housing needs through a gradually progressive process.

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